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Review Article

**THE PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS:
ARTICLE REVIEW**

Abuobaida E.E. Abukhelaif¹, Ali Moteb S Alzahrani¹, Fahad Abdullah S Alghamdi¹, Ruba Saleh S Alghamdi¹, Ahmed Ali I Alghamdi¹, Khalid Ali S Alzahrani¹, Meshari Nasser A Allakhmi¹, Fadiyah Ahmed M Shabaan²

¹ Al-Baha University, Baha, Saudi Arabia.

² Alsalam Primary Health Care Center, Al-Madina, Saudi Arabia

Abstracts:

Background: By delineating the interplay between genetic susceptibility, environmental triggers, and immune dysregulation, this theoretical framework provides a structured understanding of the pathophysiology of rheumatoid arthritis. It is a foundation for investigating potential therapeutic targets and developing interventions that address the intricate molecular and cellular processes involved in RA progression.

Objective: As we delve into the depths of RA's pathophysiology, this review aims to synthesize recent findings and seminal contributions, providing a comprehensive overview of the current understanding of the molecular and cellular mechanisms driving this complex autoimmune disorder. By unraveling these intricacies, the contribution to this effort aimed at developing targeted therapeutic interventions and advancing the management of rheumatoid arthritis.

Methodology: Comprehensive research of the pathophysiology of rheumatoid arthritis. PUBMED and Google Scholar search engines were the main used databases for the search process, and articles were collected from 1990 to 2023.

The terms used in the search were: Rheumatoid arthritis, Pathogenesis, Pathophysiology, Systemic Manifestations.

Conclusion: Unraveling the intricate pathophysiology of RA provides a foundation for advancing diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, ultimately improving the quality of life for individuals grappling with this challenging autoimmune disorder.

Keywords: Rheumatoid arthritis, Pathogenesis, Pathophysiology, Systemic Manifestations.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Abuobaida E.E. Abukhelaif,

Al-Baha University, Baha, Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, systemic autoimmune disorder characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, joint destruction, and systemic complications. This inflammatory process leads to joint pain, swelling, and stiffness, often resulting in joint deformities and erosion of cartilage and bone. RA is a systemic condition, meaning it can affect various organs and systems throughout the body, leading to extra-articular manifestations(1). The exact cause of RA is not fully understood, but its etiology involves a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and immunological factors, leading to an aberrant immune response. The pathophysiology of RA has been a subject of intense investigation, as researchers strive to decipher the intricate molecular mechanisms underlying its initiation and progression(2).

Biomarkers in Rheumatoid Arthritis:

Immunologically, RA is characterized by infiltrating inflammatory cells into the synovium, leading to the formation of a hyperplastic synovial membrane, known as the pannus. This synovial inflammation is orchestrated by various immune cells, including T cells, B cells, and macrophages, as well as the dysregulation of cytokines (1, 3). The key biomarkers in (RA) collectively illuminate the intricate mechanisms underlying the disease. Autoantibodies such as rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs) are pivotal in signaling autoimmune responses against self-antigens, particularly citrullinated proteins. This autoimmunity contributes to synovial inflammation and joint damage(4). C-reactive protein (CRP) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), as acute-phase reactants, reflect the systemic inflammatory burden, providing valuable indicators of disease activity(5). Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) play a central role in the degradation of extracellular matrix components, contributing to joint destruction(6). Pro-inflammatory cytokines, notably tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), orchestrate the perpetuation of synovial inflammation and joint pathology(7). Utilizing imaging techniques such as ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) enables visualization of structural changes, aiding in the assessment of joint damage(8). Disease activity scores (DAS28), integrating clinical and laboratory parameters, offer a comprehensive evaluation of RA activity(9). These biomarkers collectively inform the diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutic management of RA.

The Immune Dysregulation:

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is conceptualized within a theoretical framework that emphasizes immune dysregulation as the central mechanism driving the initiation and perpetuation of the disease. This framework integrates genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and aberrant immune responses into a cohesive model, shedding light on the interconnected pathways that characterize RA pathophysiology. This involves the dysregulation of immune cells and cytokines. Activated T cells, particularly CD4+ T cells, infiltrate the synovium and release pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-6**. McInnes and Schett provide an extensive overview of the immune mechanisms driving synovial inflammation and joint destruction in RA (3). The dysregulated immune response not only targets the synovium but also leads to the production of autoantibodies.

Genetic Predisposition:

Genetic studies have identified a strong association between histocompatibility complex (MHC); specific human leukocyte antigen (HLA) alleles, particularly the HLA-DRB1 locus, play a pivotal role in genetic susceptibility to RA^[1]. The shared epitope hypothesis posits that specific HLA-DRB1 alleles contribute to an increased risk of RA by influencing antigen presentation and immune responses(2). This genetic predisposition influences the presentation of autoantigen and shapes the immune response, playing a crucial role in RA pathogenesis.

Environmental Triggers:

Environmental factors, such as smoking and periodontal disease, act as triggers that can initiate or exacerbate RA in genetically predisposed individuals (10). These factors may contribute to the breakdown of immune tolerance and the activation of auto-reactive immune responses. Environmental triggers such as smoking may act in concert with genetic factors, disrupting immune tolerance and promoting autoimmunity(11). The Nurses' Health Study by Karlson *et al.* demonstrated a dose-dependent relationship between cigarette smoking and the risk of RA in female health professionals (10). Understanding the complex interplay of these predisposing factors provides a foundation for unraveling the pathophysiology of RA. Ongoing research endeavors continue to refine our knowledge, paving the way for targeted therapeutic interventions in the management of this debilitating autoimmune disorder.

Synovial Inflammation, Hyperplasia and Joint Destruction:

The hallmark of RA is chronic inflammation of the synovium, driven by infiltrating immune cells, particularly CD4+ T lymphocytes and macrophages, that orchestrate a chronic inflammatory response(3). This infiltration triggers the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), creating a local environment conducive to ongoing inflammation. The dysregulated immune response involves a complex network of cytokines and chemokines, such as CCL2 and CXCL8, further amplifying the inflammatory milieu. As the inflammation persists, synovial hyperplasia ensues, marked by the proliferation of synovial fibroblasts and the formation of an invasive tissue known as the pannus (1, 3). This hyperplastic membrane is a key contributor to joint destruction, eroding cartilage and bone. Enzymes like matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) play a crucial role in this process, degrading extracellular matrix components in the cartilage and contributing to joint degeneration. Understanding these intricate mechanisms is crucial for the development of targeted therapies aimed at interrupting synovial inflammation and hyperplasia in the management of RA(12-14). The ongoing inflammation contributes to joint destruction, cartilage degradation, and bone erosion(3).

Autoantibodies and Immune Complexes:

The production of autoantibodies, such as rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs), further amplifies the immune response in RA. Immune complexes formed by these autoantibodies contribute to joint inflammation and tissue damage(3). The presence of autoantibodies is considered not only a diagnostic marker but also a pathogenic factor in the progression of RA(1). The work by Smolen *et al.* extensively discusses the role of autoantibodies and their clinical implications in RA(1). The work by van Venrooij *et al.* discusses the diagnostic and prognostic significance of antibodies in the second-generation CCP (CCP2) test, known for its high sensitivity and specificity; the production occurs early in the course of the disease and is influenced by the presence of specific MHC class II alleles. Research has demonstrated that ACPA in the inflamed synovium binds to citrullinated antigens, forming immune complexes that contribute to the advancement of the inflammatory process (15). The study by Nell *et al.* investigates the association between autoantibodies and the progression of RA and concluded that autoantibody testing rheumatoid factors (RF) is the first of choice in early inflammatory joint disease,

followed by anti-CCP (in patients with RF, 50 U/ml or less). Finally, for the most sensitive and effective strategy for distinguishing patients with RA at high risk for poor outcomes, anti-RA33 should be used (16).

Angiogenesis:

the formation of new blood vessels, is a characteristic feature of the synovial inflammation in RA. Increased vascularity supports immune cell infiltration into the synovium, contributing to the hyperplastic changes associated with the pannus. Angiogenesis is indicative of its aggressive nature.(13)

Systemic Manifestations:

Rheumatoid arthritis is not confined solely to the joints; it is a systemic autoimmune disorder that can affect various organs and systems throughout the body. The systemic manifestations of RA extend beyond the synovium, contributing to the complexity and heterogeneity of the disease.

- **Cardiovascular Complications:**

RA is significantly associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD), constituting a notable cause of morbidity and mortality in RA patients. Chronic inflammation, a hallmark of RA, contributes to the development of atherosclerosis due to elevated levels of cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 that cause the buildup of plaques in arterial walls(17). Endothelial dysfunction also plays a crucial role in the development of cardiovascular complications in RA; as the chronic inflammation impairs the normal functioning of endothelial cells leading to reduced vasodilation, increased vascular permeability, and a pro-thrombotic state(18). Additionally, enhanced Individuals with RA have an elevated risk of myocardial infarction (MI) and stroke compared to the general population(19). Moreover, in severe cases of RA, particularly those involving rheumatoid vasculitis, inflammation can directly affect blood vessels, leading to vascular damage and potential cardiovascular complications(20).

- **Respiratory Involvement:**

Interstitial lung disease (ILD) and pleuritis are common respiratory manifestations in RA. The exact pathogenic mechanisms linking them are not fully understood, but chronic systemic inflammation in RA is believed to play a central role. The inflammatory process in RA may extend to the lungs, leading to immune cell infiltration, fibroblast activation, and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. This inflammatory cascade contributes to the development of fibrosis and scarring in the lung interstitial. Pleuritis

may cause pleuritic chest pain and, in severe cases, pleural effusions. These respiratory complications significantly contribute to the morbidity associated with RA (21, 22).

- **Hematologic Abnormalities:**

RA is associated with various hematologic manifestations, including anemia and thrombocytosis. Chronic inflammation and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin 1 (IL-1) or tumor necrosis factor (TNF) contribute to these abnormalities. Anemia of chronic disease is common and results from diversion of iron from the erythropoietic compartment into marrow macrophages which termed failure of iron utilization (23, 24).

- **Ocular Involvement:**

RA-related inflammation can extend to the episcleral (episcleritis) or the sclera (scleritis), causing redness, pain, and photophobia. Scleritis is a more severe and potentially sight-threatening condition(25). The inflammatory response involves the dilation of blood vessels, leading to the characteristic clinical features [19]. Also, it can cause uveitis which leads to redness, pain, photophobia, and blurred vision(26). In addition, RA can lead to corneal complications, including keratitis (inflammation of the cornea) and thinning of the corneal tissue. Inflammatory cells infiltrate the cornea, causing edema and compromising its transparency. These changes may result in visual disturbances and potential damage to the corneal structure. Additionally, it can also be associated with optic neuritis and retinopathy are rare but serious complications affecting the optic nerve and retina, respectively (27).

- **Psychological Impact:**

RA has significant psychological implications, contributing to increased rates of depression and anxiety among affected individuals. Chronic pain, physical disability, and the unpredictability of disease flare-ups contribute to the psychological burden. Furthermore, fatigue is a prevalent and often debilitating symptom that significantly impacts the quality of life in RA patients(28).

CONCLUSION:

Unraveling the intricate pathophysiology of RA provides a foundation for advancing diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, ultimately improving the quality of life for individuals grappling with this challenging autoimmune disorder.

REFERENCES:

1. Smolen JS, Aletaha D, McInnes IB. Rheumatoid arthritis. *The Lancet*. 2016;388(10055):2023-38.
2. Gregersen PK, Silver J, Winchester RJ. The shared epitope hypothesis. An approach to understanding the molecular genetics of susceptibility to rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum*. 1987;30(11):1205-13.
3. McInnes IB, Schett G. The Pathogenesis of Rheumatoid Arthritis. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2011;365(23):2205-19.
4. Schellekens GA, de Jong BA, van den Hoogen FH, van de Putte LB, van Venrooij WJ. Citrulline is an essential constituent of antigenic determinants recognized by rheumatoid arthritis-specific autoantibodies. *J Clin Invest*. 1998;101(1):273-81.
5. Pepys MB, Hirschfield GM. C-reactive protein: a critical update. *J Clin Invest*. 2003;111(12):1805-12.
6. Burrage PS, Mix KS, Brinckerhoff CE. Matrix metalloproteinases: role in arthritis. *Front Biosci*. 2006;11:529-43.
7. McInnes IB, Schett G. Cytokines in the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2007;7(6):429-42.
8. McQueen F, Lassere M, Edmonds J, Conaghan P, Peterfy C, Bird P, et al. OMERACT Rheumatoid Arthritis Magnetic Resonance Imaging Studies. Summary of OMERACT 6 MR Imaging Module. *J Rheumatol*. 2003;30(6):1387-92.
9. Prevoo ML, van 't Hof MA, Kuper HH, van Leeuwen MA, van de Putte LB, van Riel PL. Modified disease activity scores that include twenty-eight-joint counts. Development and validation in a prospective longitudinal study of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum*. 1995;38(1):44-8.
10. Karlson EW, Lee IM, Cook NR, Manson JE, Buring JE, Hennekens CH. A retrospective cohort study of cigarette smoking and risk of rheumatoid arthritis in female health professionals. *Arthritis Rheum*. 1999;42(5):910-7.
11. Pedersen M, Jacobsen S, Klarlund M, Pedersen BV, Wiik A, Wohlfahrt J, et al. Environmental risk factors differ between rheumatoid arthritis with and without auto-antibodies against cyclic citrullinated peptides. *Arthritis Res Ther*. 2006;8(4):R133.
12. Tak PP, Kalden JR. Advances in rheumatology: new targeted therapeutics. *Arthritis Res Ther*. 2011;13 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):S5.
13. Ballara S, Taylor PC, Reusch P, Marmé D, Feldmann M, Maini RN, et al. Raised serum vascular endothelial growth factor levels are

- associated with destructive change in inflammatory arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2001;44(9):2055-64.
14. Bartok B, Firestein GS. Fibroblast-like synoviocytes: key effector cells in rheumatoid arthritis. *Immunol Rev.* 2010;233(1):233-55.
 15. van Venrooij WJ, van Beers JJ, Pruijn GJ. Anti-CCP antibodies: the past, the present and the future. *Nat Rev Rheumatol.* 2011;7(7):391-8.
 16. Nell VP, Machold KP, Stamm TA, Eberl G, Heinzl H, Uffmann M, et al. Autoantibody profiling as early diagnostic and prognostic tool for rheumatoid arthritis. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2005;64(12):1731-6.
 17. del Rincón ID, Williams K, Stern MP, Freeman GL, Escalante A. High incidence of cardiovascular events in a rheumatoid arthritis cohort not explained by traditional cardiac risk factors. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2001;44(12):2737-45.
 18. Dimitroulas T, Sandoo A, Kitas GD. Asymmetric dimethylarginine as a surrogate marker of endothelial dysfunction and cardiovascular risk in patients with systemic rheumatic diseases. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2012;13(10):12315-35.
 19. Aviña-Zubieta JA, Choi HK, Sadatsafavi M, Etmnan M, Esdaile JM, Lacaille D. Risk of cardiovascular mortality in patients with rheumatoid arthritis: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2008;59(12):1690-7.
 20. Turesson C, Jacobsson LT, Matteson EL. Cardiovascular co-morbidity in rheumatic diseases. *Vasc Health Risk Manag.* 2008;4(3):605-14.
 21. Bongartz T, Nannini C, Medina-Velasquez YF, Achenbach SJ, Crowson CS, Ryu JH, et al. Incidence and mortality of interstitial lung disease in rheumatoid arthritis: a population-based study. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2010;62(6):1583-91.
 22. Assayag D, Lee JS, King TE, Jr. Rheumatoid arthritis associated interstitial lung disease: a review. *Medicina (B Aires).* 2014;74(2):158-65.
 23. Weiss G, Goodnough LT. Anemia of chronic disease. *N Engl J Med.* 2005;352(10):1011-23.
 24. Smith MA, Knight SM, Maddison PJ, Smith JG. Anaemia of chronic disease in rheumatoid arthritis: effect of the blunted response to erythropoietin and of interleukin 1 production by marrow macrophages. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 1992;51(6):753-7.
 25. Zafirakis P, Foster C. *Diagnosis and Treatment of Uveitis.* Saunders, Philadelphia. 2002:632-52.
 26. Dick AD, Tundia N, Sorg R, Zhao C, Chao J, Joshi A, et al. Risk of Ocular Complications in Patients with Noninfectious Intermediate Uveitis, Posterior Uveitis, or Panuveitis. *Ophthalmology.* 2016;123(3):655-62.
 27. Dammacco R, Guerriero S, Alessio G, Dammacco F. Natural and iatrogenic ocular manifestations of rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review. *Int Ophthalmol.* 2022;42(2):689-711.
 28. Matcham F, Rayner L, Steer S, Hotopf M. The prevalence of depression in rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Rheumatology (Oxford).* 2013;52(12):2136-48.